

Seismic Analysis and Design of Multi-Storeyed Building (S+G+4) using STAAD PRO

ARAVETI PEDIRAJU, MARUTLA VASEEMA, NALLAJENNU SRAVAN KUMAR REDDY

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR^{1,2,3}

peddiraju2920@gmail.com, vaseema2019@gmail.com, nsravan@svitap.ac.in

Department of Civil Engineering, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,

N.H 44, Hampapuram, Raphadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract:

Earthquakes are among the most catastrophic natural disasters that humans have ever encountered. Structures designed to withstand earthquakes should undergo thorough seismic testing, analysis, and planning. Buildings designed for seismic resistance are those that maintain their structural integrity even when the ground underneath them begins to shake. The whole structure was examined using STAAD-PRO software on a computer. Nowadays, there is a wide variety of software available, but STAAD-PRO is by far the most popular choice for building analysis and design that takes seismic pressures into account, as well as for reviewing and studying the behaviour of multi-story buildings.

In order to determine the best approach for the given structure, we run both static and dynamic analyses on the suggested design and compare the outcomes.

1. Introduction:

Seismic analysis and the design of a S+G+4 RCC building are both included in the project report. Seismic examination of this S+G+4 story building in India's Delhi zone 4 area. The seismic investigation of the S+G+4 apartment complex, which has many stories, is the focus of the current investigation. Code books and suggestions are used to get the design for the beam, column, and slab, as well as the dead load and live load that are applied.

2. Literature review:

The behaviour of G+11 multi-storeyed buildings with regular and irregular configurations under complicated earthquake conditions, with varying wind loads expected to operate concurrently with earthquake loads, was compared by Mahesh et al. (2014). This article uses ETABS and STAAD PRO to analyse the seismic and wind loads on a G+11 multi-story residential structure. We conduct static and dynamic analyses based on the premise that the material property is linear.

Using the STAAD PRO programme and varying the lateral stiffness system conditions, Patil et al. (2013) examined high-rise buildings. The response spectrum approach is used to analyse several models, which are created as brace frames and shear wall frames, respectively. An improved representation of the effects of higher vibrational modes and the real distribution of forces in the elastic range was generated by this approach.

In zones I and II, linear equivalent static analyses were conducted for regular structures up to a height of 90 metres; in zones IV and V, dynamic analyses were recommended for both regular and irregular buildings. (Mohan, 2011). According to the results of the

aforementioned research, symmetrical structures up to a height of 25 metres may make good use of the analogous static approach. The response spectrum approach is more appropriate for taller and less symmetrical structures.

Investigating the behaviour of preexisting buildings when subjected to seismic loads, Hassaballa A.E. et al. (2013) examined the seismic analysis of RC buildings. The building's frame was estimated using STAAD Pro software and examined using the Response Spectrum Method. The results of the seismic load and static load analyses of multi-story buildings showed that the response spectrum approach required high dimensions in order to withstand substantial movement.

According to IS 1893:2002 part1, Mindaye et al. (2016) used the Response spectral technique and linear analytic methodologies of equivalent static lateral forces in their study of the seismic response of G+10 RC frame residential buildings. The software used was ETAB ultimate 2015.

3. Methodology

3.1 Equivalent Lateral Force Method (Seismic Coefficient Method):

It is still often assumed in seismic analysis that the lateral force is the same as the real (dynamic) loading for most buildings. The only thing this strategy needs is a basic time frame. No need to worry about the shapes and durations of higher-order natural modes of vibration. The mass, basic period of vibration, and matching form of a structure are used to determine its base shear, which is the overall horizontal force acting on the structure. In accordance with the regulations, the base shear is spread throughout the structure's height in relation to lateral pressures.

Vertical distribution of base shear to different floor levels

$$Q_i = V_B \frac{W_i h_i^2}{\sum_{j=1}^n W_j h_j^2}$$

Where,

Q_i -Design lateral force at floor i

W_i -Seismic weight of floor i

H_i -Height of floor i measured from base, and

N -Number of stories in the building is the number of levels at which the masses are relocated.

3.2 Response Spectrum Analysis

Among its many names, response spectrum analysis includes the modal and mode superposition approaches. Any structure whose response is substantially affected by modes other than the basic one may be subjected to the approach. The idea behind this approach is that for certain types of damping—which are applicable to most buildings—it is possible to calculate the reaction in each natural mode of vibration separately, and then add them

together to get the overall response. Every mode has its own frequency (modal frequency), pattern of deformation (mode shape), and modal damping (modal damping). In the case of multi-story structures, it may be used to analyse the forces and deformations caused by medium intensity ground shaking, which results in a rather substantial but mostly linear reaction from the structure.

4. Plan and model:

Figure 1 Plan view

Figure 2 3D Modelling view

5. Results and Discussions:

Figure3:BaseShearresults

Figure4:DisplacementResultsw.r.tHeight

Figure5:BendingStressesComparison

6. Conclusions:

Static analysis yields larger displacements than dynamic analysis, which includes response spectrum and time history analysis, according to the comparison. High-rise structures need dynamic analysis since static analysis is insufficient due to the particular and nonlinear distribution of forces.

- At lower levels, the difference in displacement values between static and dynamic analysis is negligible, but it grows until it reaches its maximum on the roof or in the upper stories.

- Since the displacement values are larger in analogous static analysis compared to dynamic analysis, the findings are almost uneconomical. When comparing static and dynamic analyses, the static one yields an 11% higher base shear value.

- Axial stresses during static analysis are 87.14 percent higher than during dynamic analysis.

- The static analysis yields bending stress values that are 64.75 percent higher than the dynamic findings.

There is a 43.46% increase in x-direction displacement in static analysis compared to dynamic analysis, and a 68.54% increase in z-direction displacement in static analysis. When comparing static and dynamic analyses, the strain deformation is 65.3% higher in the former.

7. References:

- "Indian Standard of code and practice for plain and Reinforced concrete," IS-456-2000, published in 2002 by the Bureau of Indian Standards from New Delhi.

(Part 1) of IS 1893: 2016. "Requirements for Buildings to Withstand Earthquakes."

Dhanavath, STAAD Pro was used for the study and design of a structure with several stories.

Balaji.u. and selvaraasan conducted the design and analysis of a multi-story structure using ETABS, including both static and dynamic loading conditions. The G+5 residential building was analysed and designed by V. Varalaksmi.

Under the influence of seismic pressures, S. Abishek is working on a commercial building (G+1) in Hyderabad.